

Cultural Relativism and Conservative Countries: Where Does Intervention Begin?

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Introduction of Human Rights

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Introduction

Human rights are a hotly contested subject to begin with. In an ideal world, everyone would be accorded human rights simply because they exist. Yes, that is how it should be, but of course, things rarely go as planned. Numerous infractions are occurring in real time all around the world, but nothing has changed. However, when viewed from the other side, many of the core human rights principles that we Westerners hold dear are not shared by others outside the West, particularly in conservative nations. The goal of cultural relativists is for everyone to learn about one another's cultures and perspectives in addition to their own, but where does the erosion of fundamental human rights end? In this paper, I'll discuss the tension between cultural relativism and conservative nations and how it conflicts with both

Issue/Problem/Topic

The topic I've chosen to discuss is cultural relativism and conservative countries. My question is, how do cultural relativists interpret human rights in conservative countries? This is a huge issue because it has the potential to divide cultures and beliefs, as well as people fighting for their human rights. But first, let's start with some definitions on this matter. Conservatives are defined as those who oppose change or innovation and adhere to strict traditional values. Looking through the lens of a country, this would be a nation of people promoting a variety of social ideas, such as organized tradition, the military, property rights, and monarchy. Conservatives primarily seek guaranteed stability and eventually evolve in this regard. They believe in competitive, strong capitalism, the right to keep and bear arms, and oppose any form of gun control; they are opposed to anything LGBTQ+ related, have a strict ideology of the male being higher than the female in everything, and more.

Conservatives are very traditional and heavily religiously influenced. When a conservative government governs a country, it creates conflict because the government imposes its beliefs and ideologies on its citizens. There is no source of differentiation, freedom, independence, or liberty. Humans are very complex creatures with varying opinions and points of view on everything, and trying to fit them into a box will never work, which is why a lot of mini battles and human rights violations occur in these countries.

Given this information, the debate over conservative nations and cultural relativism is conflicting because the latter is all about respecting people's cultures, particularly those that are not Western. This is ideal and logical, given that the West has significant influence over many nations, but it becomes an issue once a person's rights are violated or horrible acts are committed by the governments or leaders of these nations. Mass genocide against a particular racial group or the denial of the right to an education cannot be justified as acts of "religion" or "culture"; rather, they are acts of wrongdoing and violations of human rights. In this paper, I'll go into greater detail about this problem, suggest ways to deal with it effectively, and convey my hopes for the future of conservative nations.

Research Question

As mentioned before, my main question is how cultural relativists interpret the concept of human rights in conservative countries. Given that conservative nations are the primary perpetrators of widespread human rights abuses, I'm curious about the perspectives of those who promote tolerance and understanding of non-Western ideologies on how governments in those nations, which most likely do not share Western values, treat their citizens. How can that be balanced?

Main Thesis

Cultural relativists should recognize the human rights abuses committed by conservative nations while striving for equality and liberation. Hearing everyone out goes hand in hand with conservative nations attempting to be more liberal and less set in their ways, as well as acknowledging that culture and people evolve over time, thus attempting to adapt to that.

Concepts

The concepts I'll be using to further my understanding of this issue and "What is a Human Right", "Cultural Relativisms", and "The right of citizens and the relationship of government to be governed". Let's start with what a "Human Right" is. Human rights are seen as rights (s) that should legitimately belong to every person on the planet. Giving everyone reasonable rights, regardless of their gender, ethnicity, class, or religion, just because they are people. The rights to an education, to privacy, to life, and to be free from torture and other brutal treatment are a few examples of human rights. Clearly, these rights and many others are often infringed upon in numerous nations around the world. For this reason, human rights activists exist to continue the battle and ensure that everyone is given their justifiably due rights.

The notion that a person's ideas and actions should be understood in light of their own culture is referred to as cultural relativism. Instead of judging other cultures according to one's own criteria of what is "right" and "wrong," "strange" and "normal," try to comprehend their cultural practices in their own context. Cultural relativists prioritize neutrality above everything else and work to understand everyone. They do believe, however, that the idea of human rights originates from western morality, which does not hold true for everyone in the globe.

Lastly is the right of citizens and the relationship of government to be governed. In a sense, this is the notion that the "Consent of the governed" holds, as the government's moral authority to use

state power is justified and legal only when it has the permission, or agreement, of the people it is supposed to represent. In other words, a mutual agreement between the government and its citizens to not only make legal judgments but also to rule in a way that pleases both parties.

Significance

The importance of this topic is really great. Real people in the real world are having their rights violated by conservative governments and leaders. Despite having diverse ideals and perspectives on one another, everyone needs to be accepted and valued as fellow humans. It is somewhat necessary for cultural relativists to share the same ideology. Regarding my first idea of preference, a lot of cultural relativists tend to avoid the subject of human rights because they think it is our responsibility as humans not to hold others to the same standards that we do.

Although they are ideally regarded as universal, human rights are not always strictly upheld. As an example, an article by the "Islamic Network Group," or ING, an organization for peace and face-to-face education about Muslims and the misconceptions surrounding them and other misunderstood groups, discusses how Islam is a restrictive religion that forbids its adherents from exercising their right to freedom of expression, association, assembly, and womanhood. Many other nations, both inside and outside the Middle East, including China and North Korea, fit this description. As a result, a person's rights are continuously being revoked. Unfortunately, many people tend to take basic human rights for granted until they are really violated. This is how individuals will recognize the need to speak up for their rights.

The second concept is cultural relativism, which can be tricky because remaining impartial only gets you so far. Humans tend to act more intuitively than logically, thus assuming a cultural relativist perspective will allow you to take into account of both. Cultural relativists are aware that it is against the country's established laws to enter a conservative nation and attempt to

overturn the government. Keep in mind that these conservative nations reject the majority, if not all, of the rights that Americans consider to be essential to human dignity. Cultural relativists are aware of this and believe that looking at their culture from a new angle is the best way to address this problem. To push for equality, female emancipation, and a positive shift in society's perspective. Achieving this without attempting to minimize the traditions and cultures of others. This is essential because, firstly, it prevents the other side from feeling like they are fighting against their way of daily life, and secondly, it is adaptable for everyone. Since culture is constantly evolving, it's crucial to adapt to these small and significant changes in order to maintain equality for all. ^[1]

Furthermore, the idea of a citizen's right to be governed and the interaction between governments is important to the issue since in these conservative nations, it is the government and leaders (anyone who have an immense amount of power) who violate human rights. There are many different things that might cause this, but one of the primary ones is that there isn't a pure mutual understanding between the government and its people. Intense conflict develops if laws and norms are solely made by one party (the government), rather than the people it is meant to control. This results in violations of human rights; hence, as was already established, the only way for people to know whether their rights are respected or not is if those rights are actually infringed. This is significant because knowing how conservative nations operate, it is best to have alternatives to fighting, ways to find a middle ground, and strategies to foster harmony for everybody.

[1] "Answers to Frequently Asked Questions about Islam and Muslims." Islamic Networks Group (ING), March 1, 2023.
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The level of analysis for this problem will be examined at the national level. Conservative nations and their high prevalence of human rights violations should be taken into account on a global scale; many nations operate in this way. It is wrong on any level to deny someone their human rights just because they were born in a nation with conservative values. Everyone on this planet deserves fundamental liberties. The idea that one has been wronged by the government is not just a problem in conservative nations; it is a global challenge that must be resolved in order to advance humanity.

Conclusion & Critical Reflection

In conclusion, the human race has a very long way to go, but starting somewhere can potentially generate a change for everyone in the near future. It's hard when you think about it but we live in this planet for a reason, and people on here should feel the privilege and enjoyment of living life freely and happily without writing about fundamental rights being taken away in a blink of an eye. Humans have done horrible things to other humans, but to not let the happen over and over again, a change is desperately in need to happen. Conservative countries can still be conservative in a way, but also need to be open to change and adapting to it for formulate a more sustainable nation. Culture relativists need to be more open and aware of the bad side of these countries outside of the Western viewpoint, and advocate for equality and liberation along with their voice for cultural relativism.

With all the ideas and problems surrounding IR, what I discovered is that human rights education is crucial since the people in this world can be evil. It's remarkable how few people are aware of all the rights they should have until those rights are violated. This is quite alarming. Humans are incredibly complex creatures with diverse beliefs and worldviews, so it's critical to point out

when someone is attempting to violate someone else's human rights. Despite this, I am optimistic that the world can change for the better, but it will take some time for that to begin.